
THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR, HUMAN CAPITAL THEORY, AND SOCIAL LEARNING THEORY TOWARDS ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION. THE ROLE OF ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVE ENTREPRENEURSHIP, AN ATTEMPT TOWARDS DISCUSSION: A GENERAL-REVIEW PAPER

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ABSTRACT

While doing our project on the determinants of students' intention to start their businesses, we selected the context of university students at the preparatory-level in Saudi. Applying the theory of planned behavior is found to be limited among university students at the preparatory-level. We reviewed different theories and this paper will discuss the reasons why we selected updating the theory of planned behavior over the other theories. Furthermore, Islamic entrepreneurship writing is not ignored. There is indeed an alarming concern among researchers about the

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appropriate theoretical background, by doing that we could overcome obstacles to understand the determinants of intentions among preparatory level students who are willing to start their own business. The students in that stage are neither graduates nor sufficiently skilled. Therefore, using an analytical review method, we have discussed the reasons for selecting one theoretical background over another, the role of religion in their intention. This discussion will hopefully help both the students and the policymakers, particularly the sector looking at entrepreneurs, to acquire a comprehensive view about the impact of entrepreneur education on student's intention.

Key words: Social Learning, Entrepreneurship, Human Capital

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1. INTRODUCTION

The government and the policymakers today are realizing the importance of entrepreneurs more than ever before. They are searching for alternative methods of handling the rising unemployment rate (Acs, Desai, & Hessels, 2008). The solution lies in the hands of universities, who are instructed to encourage the changing mindset of students, their attitudes, intention, and behavior towards starting their own business (Raposo & do Paço, 2011). Compared to the government sectors, small and medium enterprises are not only employing more people but are also seen as major contributors to the tax income generated in gross domestic production. Therefore, improving entrepreneurship education has become a priority. Developed countries have started introducing entrepreneurship as part of their curriculum (Duval-Couetil, 2013), as engineers or doctors will need management skills to set up their own offices or clinics respectively.

Researchers are debating the effectiveness of teaching entrepreneurship. Theoretical background and the level of students are two of the important points of the debate (Yurtkoru, Acar, & Teraman, 2014). The ability of entrepreneur education to divert students' attention towards the field of business is being questioned. The results between the students of the undergraduate level vary from the students pursuing higher education (Edelman, Manolova, Shirokova, & Tsukanova, 2016; Peterman & Kennedy, 2003; Wurthmann, 2014). Similarly, there is a difference in the result between male and female students (Bhandari, 2012; Jin, Gilmartin, Sheppard, & Chen, 2014). Entrepreneurship is widely taught among different universities around the world. This study is conducted on students intended on moving to college with a core subject. However, the students of preparatory university level have been ignored. Presently, this paper proposes to examine the impact of teaching entrepreneurship to students of that level. Worth noting, the Literature review showed that students' intention among students in developing countries is determined by religion and culture. Therefore, there is a need to explain Islamic entrepreneurship. The selection of preparatory college-level context is faced with the problem of the appropriate theoretical background, as there are many theories to underline the empirical analysis of entrepreneurship education and its relationship with student intention. Therefore, this paper aims to cover that gap by reviewing three theories- of planned behavior, human capital, and social learning. They are mostly used

among researchers criticizing these theories. The first part consists of the introduction, the objective, and the paper structure. The second part explains the three theories and the third part criticizes those theories. The fourth and last chapter presents the conclusion including the appropriate theory among the three and the reasons for that.

2. THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR

The theory of planned behavior (TPB) is one of the common theoretical backgrounds used in literature to describe the determinants of an individual's intention. This theory is related to the psychological school of thought and is a description of the link between beliefs and behavior. The theory was proposed by *Ajzen, 1985* in an article titled 'From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behavior' as an extension of the theory of reasoned actions. Before proposing the theory of reasoned actions, the determinants of intention were without the perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). In other words, the theory of planned behavior describes the intention as a result of attitudes, subject norms, and perceived behavioral control. See *Figure 1.0*

Figure 1

Source: (*Ajzen, 1985*) in an article titled 'From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behavior'

2.1. Theory of planned behavior and intention of students

Empirical studies lay stress on students' intention as a vast majority of students have not decided about stepping into the business field. Applying the theory of planned behavior to examine the impact of students' intention has been widely accepted by researchers (Fielding, McDonald, & Louis, 2008; Krueger & Carsrud, 1993; Souitaris, Zerbinati, & Al-Laham, 2007). They found that there is a relationship between attitudes, subject norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ambad & Damit, 2016; Zhang, Duysters, & Clodt, 2014). Entrepreneurship as a subject will motivate students towards transforming their intention into a habit or behavior. Family background, confidence, and fundraising skills are found to be related to the student's intention. Several empirical studies tested the theory of planned

behavior among university students from Norway, Britain, France, Turkey, Netherlands, Romania, undergraduate business students, students at the MIT School of Engineering in the USA, female business students from Dubai (Autio, H. Keeley, Klofsten, G. C. Parker, & Hay, 2001; Indarti & Krinstiansen, 2003; Indarti & Rostiani, 2011; Naktiyok, Nur Karabey, & Caglar Gulluce, 2010; Nguyen, 2018; Torres et al., 2017). The tests were conducted on a mixed group of students from the preparatory level along with students from the undergraduate level. As the preparatory level is a stage between graduating from high school and joining college, the students are yet to decide their area of concentration. This stage is a suitable area to study the determinants of students' intention using the theory of planned behavior, especially in countries suffering from the low entrepreneurship growth rate.

3. HUMAN CAPITAL THEORY

The theory of human capital investigates the efficiency of education in creating value (Tan, 2014). This theory assumes that the knowledge and skills of people are important for the economy. (Passaro, Quinto, & Thomas, 2018). The thoughts of both Adam Smith and Gary Becker arrive at a common theory that the skills required and the nature of the task are valuable to a firm. The human capital theory is one of the most important theories related to firm survival, which says that a project built by an entrepreneur is driven by the knowledge and experience of the owner. It also concludes that experiences translate into knowledge and skills. The theory is most commonly used to check the investment in education and experience. While education measures vary from years of education to completion of a university degree, the experience measures vary from years of experience to related industry work experience, entrepreneurship experience, experience in starting up a new business, and the number of management positions held.

3.1. Human capital theory and the intention of students

Unlike planned behavior, human capital theory is mostly used to explain organizational performance or management performance. This theory explains that education and training for human capital could improve the performance of the firm. It suggests that a human is valued for his skills and education which ultimately improves the performance of the firm. According to (Unger, Rauch, Frese, & Rosenbusch, 2011) there is a significant relationship between task-related human capital and entrepreneurial performance (Unger et al., 2011). It was proved by (Sonntag & Frese, 2005) that experience does not necessarily imply that a person is knowledgeable. Moreover, unlike the theory of planned behavior, this theory is not suitable to examine the relationship between the various determinants of students' intention to launch their own business. The reason is attributed to the level of students this paper is reviewing. The students preparing to get admission at the university level have not worked in any organization nor have they gained the required experience and skills necessary for the investigation. A few other research studies have no evidence of any positive relationship between employees trained in higher education institutions and organizational performance. Therefore, we have decided to ignore this theory by grounding the conceptual basis.

4. SOCIAL LEARNING THEORY

The theory of social learning assumed that observing and imitating others, changes the behavior of individuals, particularly the students. During the process of learning, rewards and punishments may impact behavior. This theory emphasizes the surroundings and interactions among students as key factors in attracting a student's attention towards a variety of choices (Wenger, 2018). The theory of social learning relates a student's judgments about his capabilities to complete a given task with his intention, which means that if he is convinced

about his capability of launching a new business this confidence may make him start the business. But if the student as an individual will not start a business thinking that he is incapable of handling it, the theory describes this as the relationship between entrepreneurship and intention. According to (Bandura, 1977), observing others while learning, could lead to a change in behavior. However, several studies prove that self-efficacy plays an important role in student intention along with the quality of teaching entrepreneurship. This theory could explain a relationship in various factors of a student's intention. Thus, this merging between social learning theory and the theory of planned behavior could provide a deeper understanding of the determinants of students' intentions. Currently, Covid-19 has converted the classroom teaching structure to online teaching, and one can see that all over the world, the mode of teaching has slowly shifted towards online teaching in a full-fledged manner. Therefore, the theory of planned behavior to examine the determinants of university students' intention at the preparatory-level is being looked into.

4.1. Social learning theory and intention of students

The application for social learning theory in entrepreneurship education is limited when compared with the theory of planned behavior. The theory is applied mostly to study in criminology and the reasons why a young criminal's intention is diverted (Pratt et al., 2010). The social learning theory is represented in variables such as peer attitudes, word of mouth, father's attitude, school mate's attitude, etc., while in contrast, social learning theory reserves the determinants of behavior to the learning process. It has been observed that social learning contributes majorly to decisions related to the career. Not only does observing role models in the family help in selecting a specific career but also being aware of certain images related to that career (see Millward, 2005). Contradicting this theory is another thought which says that apart from social learning which is applicable during higher education, noteworthy role models who readily contribute to making career decisions, play a significant role. The most important factors for a research goal are developmental and behaviorist viewpoints to improve our understanding of career-making instead of delivering vocational guidance. From the literature, we can deduce that choosing a career includes various processes that involve diverse theoretical ideas and not a general theory that people believe, exists. We adopted the theory of planned behavior, as in our study about entrepreneurial students' intention at the preparatory- university level, we found that social learning theory ignored the online environment during Covid-19.

5. ISLAMIC ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Islamic entrepreneurship is the process of starting an enterprise to produce goods or to render services that are halal to make reasonable profits. Including activities that lack consumer rights, social responsibilities, ethical values, and good business practices (Hoque, Mamun, & Mohammad Ahshanul Mamun, 2014). It's documented that people with different religions viewed entrepreneurship differently (Ramadani, Dana, Ratten, & Tahiri, 2015), religion and culture are found to play a role in determining the intention of students towards starting their business (Davis, 2013; Mukhtar & Butt, 2012). Furthermore, Islamic economic research has shown concern of injecting economic growth by encouraging small and medium enterprises, the main guidelines of Islam prohibit activities of business involving alcoholic or any product prohibited by Islamic law (Ahmed, 2010). Therefore, an advanced theoretical and conceptual view is under investigation by current researchers.

5.1. Religion role and intention of students

Religion plays an important role in the character of many individuals, Islamic teaching for example prohibits starting business particularly those involved for the sake of gaining interest rate. Indeed, Islamic values and Islamic practices are found to influence the attitudes of Muslim entrepreneurs, there is indeed a particular Islamic approach to entrepreneurship (Kayed & Hassan, 2013), attitudes are found to mediate the relationship between Islamic values, Islamic practices, and entrepreneurial intention (Ratten, Alamanda, Ramadani, Hashani, & Anggadwita, 2017; Vargas-Hernández, Noruzi, & Sariolghalam, 2010). Furthermore, work ethics are found to mediate the relationship between creativity and intention, other papers found that people's choices are impacted by religion and religious commitments (Kayed & Hassan, 2010). Based on that, there is ample room to develop an updated conceptual framework that considers injecting the theory of planned behavior with religious practices and religious values.

6. CONCLUSION

This general-review paper is meant to describe the underlining theoretical background formed to examine the determinants of students' intentions at the preparatory- university level. The students at this level are considered important as they are exploring a collection of topics of which entrepreneurship is one. The theoretical interpretation is performed before the investigation. The reader browsing the literature may find different theories explaining the determinants of intentions among students in general- for example, the theory of planned behavior, human capital theory, and social learning theory. We have examined these theories to justify the reason for adopting one theory over the other. The preparatory-level students are different from those in the undergraduate or higher education level. The review resulted in selecting the theory of planned behavior over the others because the determinants in human capital theory require students to be knowledgeable and skilled in entrepreneurship whereas students considered at the beginning of the university level, acquire neither experience nor skills. Similarly, the theory of social learning gave priority to social activities while studying, which may be attributed to the change in students' behavior while starting their business. The students at the preparatory level are from the same level of study, and their social behavior is mostly related to social media activities, sports, and playing games. Therefore, changing of intention may not suit the explanation of the social learning theory. Meanwhile, religion plays an important role in determining students' intentions thus researchers had better consider the unions of context particularly in developing countries where ethical values may play a role. This paper may help those students who are struggling to search for a theoretical background which will explain the empirical analysis in determinants of students' intention.

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